

A Study on The Economic Impact of KCC Loans in Uttar Pradesh, India to Introduce Financial Mobility For Farmers

Paper Id : 17775 Submission Date : 07/06/2023 Acceptance Date : 20/06/2023 Publication Date : 25/06/2023

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10450782

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/shinkhlala.php#8>

Akhilesh Meena

Research Scholar
Department Of Economics
Central University Of
Haryana
Mahendergarh, Haryana,
India

Abstract The present research study has discussed with respect to the benefits of the KCC scheme especially for farmers in the UP. It has been determined that this loan scheme has been formed with the joint support of the “Public Sector Bank” and NABARD. A secondary quantitative methodology has been adopted for the study. Farmers can achieve essential benefits with the utilization of this beneficiary scheme. Therefore, it has been understood that the farmers can effectively increase the margins of their profit and the rate of productivity. Besides, the study has stated the probable component of the suitability of the credit flow in development to the rural zone in the UP.

Keywords Kisan Credit Card (KCC), Public Sector Banks (PSB), Department of Agriculture Cooperation & Farmers Welfare (DAC&FW), Rural Regional Banks (RRBs)

Introduction KCC scheme has credit limits that are basically short-term with respect to crops and loans. It has been found that farmers generally have KCC credit that is surrounded under the insurance of personal accidents and it is approximately Rs. 50,000 for endless disability and it defines at the risk of Rs. 25,000 ultimately. It has been found that farmers with regard to this scheme can benefit from the insurance-free loan that is up to Rs. 1 lakh. In this context, the present study thoroughly discusses the impact of financial mobility of the “Kisan Credit Card (KCC)” loans on farmers in UP.

Aim of study 1. To determine the role of KCC scheme on farmers in the UP 2. To define the pattern that KCC scheme provides benefits to farmers in the UP 3. To analyze the challenges in the implementation of the KCC scheme on farmers in the UP 4. To provide suitable recommendations for the utilization of the KCC scheme among farmers in the UP

Review of Literature

KCC and its Influence on Financial Involvement in India

The “**Kisan Credit Card (KCC)**” scheme is defined as an innovative way that assists farmers in India that fulfils the requirement of agricultural production. The government of India has inaugurated the KCC scheme after a discussion with the NABARD and RBI for supplying term loans with regard to agricultural needs. Most Indian Banks, RRBs, especially cooperative banks take part in these entities. The program of KCC has been executed thoroughly in Uttar Pradesh and various banks have given KCC loans to approximately 6.95% of farmers (Mishra and Chaudhary, 2021). Therefore, it has been found that based on the statement of the “**Public Sector Banks**” and NABARD, approximately “**187.03 lakh KCC loans**” with a credit limit of up to Rs. 1.76 lakh crore have been approved for farmers in Uttar Pradesh (UP). It has been found that UP has issued more than “**10 million credit cards**” with respect to the KCC scheme in the financial year of 2020 (Gautam et al. 2022). Furthermore, the KCC scheme has been properly designed to accumulate the requirements of consumption of farmers and their domestics. The KCC is basically planned to deliver the working capital for managing farm investments and agricultural activities (Umadevi and Saritha, 2022). Thus, it has been noted that the application of this scheme aims to accumulate the requirement for investment credit for agricultural purposes. The exertion KCC scheme has provided essential advantages to farmers in the UP as they can develop reliable profit margins and have delivered outstanding agricultural loans by around “**6.97 trillion rupees**” (Bijoy, 2017). Hence, it has been stated that the administrative body in India has improved the monetary inclusions due to the involvement of KCC loans.

Effect of the Kisan Credit Card (KCC) Scheme on the rural credit

The holders of KCC have protected against the losses of finances by around Rs. 50,000 against many severe cases. The farmer households in the UP have operated the KCC scheme for achieving the credit that gratifies the agricultural activities and requirements (Singh and Prakash, 2022). Therefore, it has been understood that the implementation of the KCC scheme has ensured the needs of working capital in addition to the crop cultivation, expenses of post-harvest, animal husbandry and consumption requirements. It has been estimated that more than “10 million credit cards” were effective under the scheme of KCC in the UP in the fiscal year of 2022 (Statista.com, 2023). Furthermore, it has been pursued by “Maharashtra” and “Andhra Pradesh” by around “6.9 million” and “6.2 million” subsequently.

Figure 1: Invention tool for “Farmers Credit System” due to “Kisan Credit Card”

(Source: Adhikary et al. 2013)

The participation of female farmers has increased from approximately “43%” in 2014 to approximately “76%” in 2017 due to the enhancement of the KCC scheme. Co-operative banks have played a significant function in delivering affordable credit with regard to the interest of KCC loans (Adhikary et al. 2013). Hence, it has been identified that the KCC scheme with the support of Cooperative banks has been determined an indispensable element to accelerate the economic reforms. It has been found that “Sharecroppers”, “tenant farmers” and “oral lessees” are completely suitable for the scheme of the KCC (Mehta et al. 2016). Therefore, it has been understood that farmers in the UP have typically involved in addition to allied activities including animal husbandry with the activities of non-farm including fishermen.

The economic influence of the KCC Scheme on the profitability of crops in the Deoria district of UP

The KCC scheme has comprised around 60% addition to the outstanding credit with the support of the worth of the banks that consists of approximately “Rs. 15.9 lakh crore” for agricultural activities. The entire expenditure of sugarcane was calculated by approximately “Rs. 114762.58” with respect to the holders of the KCC in comparison to the holders of the non-KCC by around “Rs. 107979.88” (Kumar et al. 2021). Furthermore, it has been estimated that the average income for the KCC holders in Deoria, UP was about “Rs. 111049.52” rather than the average income of non-KCC holders by around “Rs. 92924.72”. Besides, the entire expenditure of wheat was valued at approximately “Rs. 53850.21” for the KCC holders that are greater than the expenditures of the non-KCC holders by approximately “Rs. 51720.97” (Sharma, 2016). Moreover, it has been stated that the productivity of “sugarcane”, “paddy” and “wheat crop” has enhanced with the improvement of the farm size. The state government of the UP has composed the “Uttar Pradesh Agricultural Policy 2013” that mainly aims at converting the entire state into a “Grainary of the Nation” (Upagriparadarshi.gov.in, 2023). It makes sure the nutritional security that helps in improving the standard of the village lifestyle with overall and sustainable development. Moreover, the state government in the UP has implemented a suitable policy for agriculture in achieving the proper loan of crops with the help of the KCC scheme (Basak, 2017). Thus, it has been understood that the KCC loan improves the productivity of agriculture and the system of profitable farming.

Effect of Financial Technology Including KCC Loans on sustainable development of Farmers in UP, India

The application for the KCC loans helps in evaluating various and effective technology with regard to finances. Moreover, it has been stated that the implementation of the KCC loans for farmers in UP, India has assisted in their sustainable development (Bergvinson, 2018). Therefore, this contemporary technology with regard to agriculture has directed the improvement of productivity and profitability. The main vision of the KCC scheme has provided the concessional conventional agri-credit with respect to all farmers and also deliver the short or long-term cultivation necessities (Agricoop. nic. in, 2021). Hence, it has been identified that ISS is obtainable for farmers that indicates the short-term loans by approximately “Rs. 3.00 lakh”. Furthermore, the “**Department of Agriculture Cooperation & Farmers Welfare (DAC&FW)**” has initiated the second stage of the KCC loans. The government of India has provided directives and proper circulars to enable KCC saturation (Divya and Jahan, 2017). Therefore, it has been recognized that the utilization of the KCC scheme has helped in upgrading the processing expenditures, assessment, charges of ledger folio and many service charges with regard to the KCC renewal.

Figure 2: Influence of Lending with the Help of the “Kisan Credit Cards” in Rural India

(Source:Padma and Rao, 2017)

Besides, it has been found that the “**Department of Financial Services (DFS)**” has delivered universal access to concessional credit for “**Animal Husbandry**”, “**Dairy**” and “**Fisheries**”. The utilization of the KCC scheme helps in estimating the essential entrepreneurship skills for agriculture (Padma and Rao, 2017). Hence, it has been understood that the implementation of the KCC loans helps in evaluating sustainable resources and proper liquidity in marketing.

Methodology The present research has applied the “Interpretivism Research Philosophy” that is totally reliant on the major policies. The usage of the “Interpretivism Research Philosophy” specifically establishes the consequential measurements and proper reactions (HR and Aithal, 2022). Therefore, it has been determined that the application of this research philosophy is intuitive and has considerable philosophies with reference to this particular matter. On the contrary, quantitative research helps in gathering and describing the analytical assertions in the matter of particular concern. The exertion of a “quantitative research approach” grants a restricted creation and the participants have restricted options for providing the answers (Pentang and Pentang, 2021). Likewise, it has been identified that this specific matter has not applied qualitative research as it specifically lacks the actual occurrences and forgets to regard the documented attitudes with respect to the expansion of statements and consequences. It has been defined that the implementation of the “Inductive Research approach” simplifies the examination to collect appropriate pieces of argument and important characteristics. The use of the “Inductive Research approach” administers in production of suitable statements and practical approaches that empower the entire research to evolve adjustable (Walter and Ophir, 2019). Therefore, it has been recognised that this contemporary investigation has employed this research approach to design restorative and prompt speculation. This article has employed the “Descriptive Research Design” for accumulating superficial rationality. The implementation of the “Descriptive Research Design” helps the entire

research to maintain the effectiveness of the costs and correspondingly provides an authentic statement (Doyle et al. 2020). Hence, it has been verified that this analysis has accumulated numerous scientific and accurate sensations with the assistance of this specific research design.

Result and Discussion

Findings

It has been found that the implementation of the KCC scheme has facilitated the enhancement of agricultural productivity. There are many financial institutions such as the “*State Bank of India (SBI)*”, “*United Bank of India (UBI)*” and “*Assam Gramin Bikash Bank (AGVB)*” have issued the KCC scheme (Aau. ac. in, 2015). Correspondingly, it has been understood that these banks have authorised “*crop loans*” for agriculturalists under various projects with regard to the Government of India. Furthermore, the financial agencies may get essential help and support that also helps them to find out the effective solutions with respect to the major problems. The aspect of the significance of the credit flow in addition to the rural sector in the UP, decreases the reliability of farmers with regard to the credit sources of the non-institutional. Similarly, it has been found that the implementation of the KCC scheme helps in offerings probable recommendations to the policymakers (Pathroseet al. 2015). Therefore, it has been recognized that the exertion of the KCC scheme has emerged the convenient products with respect to banking. Moreover, the scheme of the KCC has ranked the first position with the superior “*mean score of 13.446*”. In the case of awareness, the KCC loans have ranked third along with the “*mean score of 9.931*”. The application of KCC scheme has not thoroughly impacted one dimension and category of the family members in the matter of the agricultural field. There are various data has been found with regard to the sanctioned amount of KCC by various banks;

Year	KCC issued in Commercial Banks (Lakhs)	Amount sanctioned in Commercial Banks (Rs. Cr)
2012-13	82.43	72625
2013-14	76.39	70145
2014-15	218.06	73564
2015-16	225.25	658456.5
2016-17	250.37	70555.69
2017-18	456.23	89720.63
2018-19	786.35	7854.23
2019-20	45.69	6534.85
2020-21	456.35	720.64
2021-22	50.63	564.75
2022-23	76.65	6457.52
Statistical value of sanctioned amount in commercial bank		
Mean		96108.98273
Median		70145
Mode		#N/A
Standard deviation		189931.5302

Table 1: KCC issues and amount sanctioned in commercial banks

Year	KCC issued in Cooperative Banks (Lakhs)	Amount sanctioned in Cooperative Banks (Rs. Cr)
2012-13	29.79	11174
2013-14	26.89	10825
2014-15	17.32	7322
2015-16	28.9	105463
2016-17	30.2	126459
2017-18	72.5	200557
2018-19	60.2	225798
2019-20	27.89	364598
2020-21	82.61	25000
2021-22	90.45	64570
2022-23	64.37	70055
Statistical value of sanctioned amount in commercial bank		
Mean		110165.5455
Median		70055
Mode		#N/A
Standard deviation		113026.806

Table 2: KCC issues and amount sanctioned in cooperative banks

Year	KCC issued in RRBs (Lakhs)	Amount sanctioned in RRBs (Rs. Cr)
2012-13	20.3	12836
2013-14	21.35	20689
2014-15	24.96	24248
2015-16	121.81	77118.42
2016-17	125.86	78005.26
2017-18	130.65	82500.56
2018-19	135.7	85526.76
2019-20	145.65	88200.5
2020-21	150.7	90754.62
2021-22	155.98	92456.45
2022-23	160.65	95780.52
Statistical value of sanctioned amount in commercial bank		
Mean		68010.55364
Median		82500.56
Mode		#N/A
Standard deviation		31924.98462

Table 3: KCC issues and amount sanctioned in RRBs

Year	KCC issued in Aggregate (Lakhs)	Amount sanctioned in Aggregate (Rs. Cr)
2012-13	129.52	96635
2013-14	124.63	101659
2014-15	124.82	105134
2015-16	736.3	841038.03
2016-17	800.4	85467.47
2017-18	850.5	86000
2018-19	855.49	87456
2019-20	860.52	89000
2020-21	870.56	92546
2021-22	888.42	92000
2022-23	900.3	95437
		98013
Statistical value of sanctioned amount in commercial bank		
Mean		155865.4583
Median		93991.5
Mode		#N/A
Standard deviation		215861.1253

Table 4: KCC issues and amount sanctioned in Aggregate

A revised scheme of the KCC was evaluated in March 2012 that replaced the passbook of the KCC with the help of the “**ATM-cum-debit-card (Smart card)**”. The “**agricultural credit flow**” in 2012-13 was restored at approximately “**Rs. 5, 75,000 crores**” (Patil *et al.* 2016). Thus, it has been estimated that the agri-loans have benefited farmers in the UP through the working capital of the KCC loans. Farmers have achieved the KCC loans at the allotment interest rate of approximately “**7% per annum**” with respect to the loan of up to “**Rs. 3 lakhs**”. The farmers have been extremely satisfied with obtaining the effective loan from the KCC that was ranked with the “**mean score of 4.55**” (Tcarts. in, 2019). Furthermore, it has been described that the KCC scheme mainly focuses on delivering the probable and essential support of timely credit to the systems of banking, especially for the farmers. The amount with respect to the credit limit has been provided with the credit limit and was determined by the “**District Level Technical Committee**” (Gupta, 2018). Correspondingly, it has been demonstrated that the taking procedure of this particular loan is quite difficult for the farmers and there is no limitation in time with respect to the loan disbursement. The limit of the “**Collateral free loan**” with regard to the “**short-term agri-credit**” has been enlarged from approximately “**Rs. 1.00 lakh**” to “**Rs. 1.60 lakhs**” with the help of the RBI (Waikar and Karmarkar, 2018). Thus, it has been estimated that the KCC scheme has been implemented by “**commercial banks**”, “**Cooperative banks**” and “**Rural Regional Banks (RRBs)**”. It has been stated that the KCC loan has been administered within 14 days with regard to the permit of the assembled application. The joint borrowers get essential benefits from the application of this effective scheme of the KCC. Therefore,

It has been stated that the exertion of the KCC scheme may enable the disbursement process that is hassle-free and a standard repayment loan. Besides, the policy of KCC was authorized by the "**Finance Minister**" and modifies the financial and social status in addition to the living standard.

Discussion

It has been discussed that the "**Kisan Credit Card (KCC)**" scheme is described as an imaginative way that helps farmers in India that achieving the necessity of agricultural production. The administrative body of India has emerged the KCC scheme after a conversation with the NABARD and RBI for providing term loans with respect to agricultural deficiencies. Most Indian Banks, RRBs, predominantly cooperative banks have participated in the entities. Likewise, it has been comprehended that the financial organizations have confirmed "**crop loans**" for planters under various schemes with reference to the Government of India. Moreover, the financial mechanisms may get fundamental help and consent that also assists them to point out effective explanations with reference to the major annoyances. The element of the effectiveness of the credit flow in expansion to the rural sector in the UP reduces the dependability of farmers with reference to the credit citations of the non-institutional. Besides, it has been discovered that the implementation of the KCC undertaking assists in offerings potential propositions to the policymakers. The effort KCC scheme has delivered essential benefits to agriculturalists in the UP as they can generate dependable profit margins and have provided outstanding farming loans of about "**6.97 trillion rupees**". Therefore, it has been articulated that the government in India has enhanced the financial inclusions due to the implementation of the KCC loans. KCC loans assist in considering various and influential technology with reference to monetary aspects. Furthermore, it has been articulated that the performance of the KCC loans for growers in UP, India has helped in their tolerable development. Similarly, this contemporary automation with reference to agriculture has produced modification of productivity and advisability. The prominent concept of the KCC method has supplied the concessional established agri-credit with regard to all agriculturalists and also provides short or long-term cultivation conditions.

It has been discussed that the boundary of the "**Collateral free loan**" with reference to the "**short-term agri-credit**" has been broadened from approximately "**Rs. 1.00 lakh**" to "**Rs. 1.60 lakhs**" with the support of the RBI. Hence, it has been calculated that the KCC scheme has been executed by "**commercial banks**", "**Cooperative banks**" and "**Rural Regional Banks (RRBs)**". It has been expressed that the KCC loan has been distributed within 14 days with reference to the access of the collected aspects. The joint borrowers get introductory advantages from the utilization of this influential technique of the KCC. The significant opinion of the KCC scheme has provided the concessional customary agri-credit with regard to all agriculturalists and also provides short or long-term cultivation conditions. Therefore, it has been recognized that ISS is attainable for farmers that characterize short-term borrowings by approximately "**Rs. 3.00 lakh**". Moreover, the "**Department of Agriculture Cooperation & Farmers Welfare (DAC&FW)**" has started the second scene of the KCC loans. The government of India has delivered messages and proper handouts to promote KCC saturation. Hence, it has been identified that the application of the KCC scheme has been administered in boosting the processing expenses, estimates, accounts of archives folio and many courtesy charges with respect to the renewal of the KCC. Therefore, it has been understood that the implementation of the KCC scheme has ensured the needs of working capital in addition to the crop cultivation, expenses of post-harvest, animal husbandry and consumption requirements. It has been assessed that more than "**10 million credit cards**" were influential under the undertaking of KCC in the UP in the revenue year of 2022. Similarly, it has been courted by "**Maharashtra**" and "**Andhra Pradesh**" of about "**6.9 million**" and "**6.2 million**" thoroughly.

Conclusion Based on the above discussion, it can be concluded that the KCC scheme has been formed with the joint support of the "Public Sector Banks" and NABARD. It ranges approximately "187.03 lakh KCC loans" with a credit limitation of up to "Rs. 1.76 lakh crore" have been authorized for agriculturalists in Uttar Pradesh (UP). Besides, the present research has used different techniques in methodology that thoroughly indicate the purpose and factors of this specific matter. It has been encountered that farmers with reference to this scheme can gain profit from the sufficient loan that is free from insurance that ranging

approximately Rs. 1 lakh. The component of the usefulness of the credit flow in development to the rural zone in the UP decreases the reliability of farmers with respect to the credit sources of the non-institutional. Furthermore, it has been found that the performance of the KCC commission administers subscription probable recommendations to the legislator.

- References**
1. Aau.ac.in, (2015). Impact of Credit on Agricultural Production with Special Reference to Crop Loan and KCC Scheme. Available at: http://www.aau.ac.in/data/reports/KCC_FINAL_REPORT.pdf [Accessed on: 7-06-2023]
 2. Adhikary, M.L., Bagli, S. and Dutta, P., 2013. An Insight into the Financial Inclusion of the States in India. *Journal of Social and Economic Development*, 15(1), pp.50-66.
 3. Agricoop.nic.in, (2021). ANNUAL REPORT 2020-21. <https://agricoop.nic.in/Documents/annual-report-2020-21.pdf> [Accessed on: 7-06-2023]
 4. Basak, N., 2017. Financial trend and risk association in Indian agricultural Credit: A study. *ZENITH International Journal of Business Economics & Management Research*, 7(10), pp.97-107.
 5. Bergvinson, D., 2018. Science & Technology and Startups in Agriculture.
 6. Bijoy, K., 2017. Financial Inclusion in India and PMJDY: A Critical Review. *ICITKM*, pp.39-46.
 7. Divya, U. and Jahan, N.F., 2017. Financial Inclusion Initiatives in India and its Contribution towards Banking Sector Reform. *Adarsh Journal of Management Research*, pp.200-205.
 8. Doyle, L., McCabe, C., Keogh, B., Brady, A. and McCann, M., 2020. An overview of the qualitative descriptive design within nursing research. *Journal of Research in Nursing*, 25(5), pp.443-455.
 9. Gautam, R.S., Rastogi, S., Bhimavarapu, V.M. and Rawal, A., 2022, September. Financial technology and its influence on India's sustainable development. In *2022 IEEE 10th Region 10 Humanitarian Technology Conference (R10-HTC)* (pp. 118-123). IEEE.
 10. Gupta, J., 2018. Government Initiatives for Financial Inclusion in India. *Asian Journal of Research in Business Economics and Management*, 8(2), pp.32-41.
 12. HR, G. and Aithal, P.S., 2022. Why is it Called Doctor of Philosophy and Why Choosing Appropriate Research Philosophical Paradigm is Indispensable During Ph. D. Program in India?. *International Journal of Philosophy and Languages (IJPL)*, 1(1), pp.42-58. (interpretivism)
 13. Kumar, H., Kumar, A., Pal, V.K., Verma, S.C. and Rawat, V.K., 2021. Economic impact of kisan credit card scheme on profitability of crops in Deoria district of Uttar Pradesh. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(9), pp.569-588.
 14. Mehta, D., Trivedi, H. and Mehta, N.K., 2016. Indian kisan credit card scheme: An analytical study. *BRAND. Broad Research in Accounting, Negotiation, and Distribution*, 7(1), pp.19-23.
 15. Mishra, J. and Chaudhary, A.K., 2021. Kisan Credit Card and its Impact on Financial Inclusion in India. *International Journal of Scientific and Management Research*, 5, pp.80-86.
 16. Padma, M.S.N. and Rao, G.S., 2017. ROLE OF COOPERATIVE BANKS IN MICRO FINANCE. *Editorial Board*, 6(8), p.201.
 17. Pathrose, E.P., Baby, A. and Maheshwari, U., 2015. A study on the challenges faced by customers in financial inclusion. *International Journal of scientific research and management (IJSRM)*, 3(1), pp.1989-1995.
 18. Patil, S., Jha, A. and Jha, A.K., 2016. Role of financial agencies in integrating small farmers into a sustainable value chain: a synthesis-based on successful value chain financing efforts. *Current Science*, pp.2082-2090.
 19. Pentang, J.T. and Pentang, J., 2021. Quantitative data analysis. *Holy Angel University Graduate School of Education: Research and academic writing*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.23906.45764>, p.1. (quantitative)
 20. Sharma, M.P., 2016. Comprehensive study of Kisan Credit Card at Central Bank of India-A useful credit tool for rural development. *IBMRD's Journal of Management & Research*, 5(1), pp.21-29.
 21. Singh, S.P. and Prakash, V., 2022. An Empirical Study on the Impact of Kisan Credit Card Scheme in the light of Rural Credit. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, pp.1472-1480.
 22. Statista.com, (2023). Number of Kisan Credit Cards (KCC) across India in financial year 2022, by leading state. Available at: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1245872/india-number-of-kisan-credit-cards-by-state/#:~:text=In%20financial%20year%202022%2C%20over,and%206.2%20million%20cards%20respectively.> [Accessed on: 7-06-2023]
 23. Tcarts.in, (2019). FARMERS' ATTITUDE TOWARDS KISAN CREDIT CARD SCHEME IN TAMILNADU – A STUDY WITH REFERENCE TO MADURAI DISTRICT. Available at: https://tcarts.in/research/research/phd_synopsis_mang.pdf [Accessed on: 7-06-2023]
 24. Umadevi, C. and Saritha, P., 2022. Marketing of Products and Services by Commercial Banks for Financial Inclusion In India-A Decennium Study. *Academy of Marketing Studies Journal*, 26(S3).
 26. Upagripardarshi.gov.in, (2023). Agriculture Department, Uttar Pradesh. Available at: <https://upagripardarshi.gov.in/StaticPages/KisanCreditCard.aspx> [Accessed on: 7-06-2023]
 26. Waikar, V. and Karmarkar, Y., 2018. Financial Inclusion-A Study of Awareness Level of People in Indore District. *Asian Journal of Management*,

P: ISSN No. 2321-290X

RNI No. UPBIL/2013/55327

VOL.- X , ISSUE- X June - 2023

E: ISSN No. 2349-980X

Shrinkhla Ek Shodhparak Vaicharik Patrika

9(1), pp.1-7. 27. Walter, D. and Ophir, Y., 2019. News frame analysis: An inductive mixed-method computational approach. *Communication Methods and Measures*, 13(4), pp.248-266. (inductive)